

Health Seeking Behaviours of the Aged Population in Nigeria

Akeem Olalekan Ayub

Sociology Department

Federal University Gusau, Zamfara, Nigeria

E-mail: *ayubakeemola@fugusau.edu.ng*

Rahamatu Shamsiyyah Iliya

Distance Learning Centre

Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

E-mail: *rshamsiyyah.iliya@abudlc.ed.ng*

Usman Abubakar

Sociology Department

Federal University Gusau, Zamfara, Nigeria

E-mail: *uskakagida1@gmail.com*

Abstract

The health problems, either illnesses or losses, facing the world's ageing population continue to multiply even though they are against the wishes and best interests of the people. Acute illness comes with many problems, and it may be necessary to keep one's emotions, self-image, abilities, and relationships in shape while dealing with the disease. The tendency of older people to seek medical attention is one of the most significant factors that play a role in the severity of the condition. Thus, this paper assessed older people's health-seeking behaviours (HSB) by focusing on the factors that facilitate and delay access to healthcare needs to ameliorate the severity of health challenges for optimal social functioning. The paper employs analytical methods and collates data from various scholarly works on the internet. It was discovered that factors that significantly affect HSB among the aged include the types of health facilities, the distance to the nearest health facility, ignorance of disease, poverty, poor attitudes of health workers, lengthy treatment process, religion, marital status, and lack of support. It was also established that physical, socio-economic, cultural, and even political factors could all play a role in influencing an individual's health behaviour. Similarly, the utilisation of a health care system is contingent on the levels of education, economic factors, cultural beliefs and practice, environment, knowledge about the facilities, gender issues, the political climate, and the health care system itself. This paper concludes that age-related health crises affect older people's HSB, particularly their well-being, social interactions, decision-making, and self-control. Therefore, it is recommended that older people should seek more information about their health and exercise daily to stay energetic,

independent, and happy; maintain a healthy lifestyle; and prioritise preventative health behaviours by becoming immunised for health emergencies.

Keywords: Aged population, ageing, health, health-seeking behaviour, old age, older people

Introduction

Old age is a global issue that governments at all levels are addressing. Increased population ageing is a human success story, a reason to celebrate public health, medical advancements, and economic and social progress over diseases, injuries, and early deaths (United Nations, 2019). In Africa, and especially Nigeria, old age is a blessing since the elderly benefit their communities and form the council of elders, keepers of traditional values, and upholders of history, customs, and cultural values. Old age brings many health concerns, so celebrating the triumph has been difficult. According to Mudiare (2013), the aged endure physical and psychological changes that cause non-communicable diseases and urinary tract infections. Every young person today will grow old and live in rural or metropolitan areas depending on their social chances. Age brings physical, mental, and social changes and needs that are well-known to people. Thinking about ageing is part of being human. Thus, experiences and knowledge gained along the way are transferred to younger family members through preserved knowledge, notes and traditions for future generations (Olayiwola *et al.*, 2013).

Historical views about ageing ranged from ritual deaths to respect, acknowledgement,

marginalisation, discrimination, and ageism. Biological changes in an ageing organism were noticeable, and the closeness of death encouraged explorers to find an elixir of youth to lengthen life and reduce senior ailments. Increasing life expectancy exposes the elderly to geriatric ailments that require speedy and positive HSBs. These behaviours are influenced by many factors, including systemic and individual approaches to prevent older people's health challenges. Based on this, individuals at all levels devise different means to remain healthy and sometimes are supported by different organisations to promote positive HSB among them. The Federal Ministry of Health aimed to develop six regional geriatric centres in tertiary hospitals to improve older people's health (Agency Report, 2019). The centres planned to address the health and social requirements of the elderly in the country, as well as their developmental difficulties. This project indicates that Nigeria's aged population suffers health challenges that require a systematic strategy to promote healthy ageing.

As international agencies focus on disease management and primary health care, nations must provide comprehensive senior care. Existing older adult programs have technical and resource efficiency problems. In underdeveloped

countries like Nigeria, governmental and public policies rarely address socio-economic and gender concerns that affect geriatric health. In Nigeria, older people lack essential health, medical care, and social assistance, negatively impacting their health-seeking behaviour (HSB) (Mudiare, 2013). Growing old comes with lots of challenges, although the health-seeking behaviour (HSB) of the aged population is crucial for optimal health. Therefore, poor health seeking can exacerbate ageing suffering and impairment. Older persons have more underlying issues regarding treatment seeking, including illiteracy, family structure, misconceptions, and funding (Lloyd-Sherlock, 2022). As unproductive elders, they may endure financial burdens and social dependency owing to disease and health care. The attitudes of healthcare professionals and older people influence long-term ageing healthcare treatment seeking. Therefore, this paper focuses on the HSBs of older people to determine the challenges faced while growing old and the possibility of as.

Literature Review

It is challenging to develop a universal operational definition of the process of HSB due to the diverse ways in which it has been researched up to this point because of the expansive nature of the health-seeking process. HSBs are actions undertaken to care for, maintain, and uphold one's health, regardless of current health status (Bausell and Bausell, 1987). Poortaghi *et al.* (2015) defined HSB as a multi-dimensional concept which relies on time and context. Tipping (2000) conceptualised HSB as

decision-making for healthcare at the household level, where the decisions made encompass all available options, whether it will be public, private, modern, or traditional. HSB is the behaviour of a person actively searching for different ways to be able to achieve higher-level wellness (Hampshire *et al.*, 2011).

In several other research, the terms “health-seeking” and “help-seeking” are used interchangeably. The tendency of older people to seek medical attention is one of the most significant factors that play a role in the severity of the condition. When a person chooses or does an activity to improve, regain, or preserve their health and ward off sickness, this is referred to as 'HSB. This often plays a role in determining whether they go to a public or private institution for medical care. Traditional medicines, self-medication, and home treatments may not appeal to many people (Chauhan, 2015). Understanding, direction, treatment, and general support are all included in HSB, which is any action of actively seeking assistance from healthcare providers or trusted persons in the community. Different people will approach the treatment of their symptoms in different ways based on their own best judgment. These behaviours are known as HSBs and are impacted by the type of care individuals prefer to receive to address their health concerns (Rickwood and Thomas, 2012).

HSBs include modifying eating habits, performing regular exercise, consulting, utilising professional care, and early detection of health crises based on their symptoms (Doshi *et al.*, 2010). HSBs play out in situations where people

control their symptoms with the help of both lay and professional resources (Shaw et al., 2018). HSBs are linked to a variety of health disorders because they provide more efficient use of medical treatment before the onset of illness (Bourne, 2009). However, its efficacy could be affected by factors like people's histories, health literacy levels, and environments. HSB, as the process of illness response, is rooted especially in psychology; look at HSBs more generally; draw out the factors which enable or prevent people from making "healthy choices" in their lifestyle behaviours or their use of medical care and treatment. HSB is conceptualised as a "sequence of remedial actions" taken to rectify "perceived ill-health" (Ahmed et al., 2000). In the second approach, the latter part of the definition, responding specifically to perceived ill-health, may be dropped as a broader perspective on affirmative, health-promoting behaviours is adopted.

Researchers have shown interest in the factors that encourage individuals to use health services and change their behaviour regarding their health. Many studies have been conducted in various nations, focusing on a particular facet of this ongoing dispute. In the context of this investigation, they may be categorised in a somewhat simplified manner as one of two categories, which closely coincide with a distinction that Tipping and Segall discovered (1995). First, some studies emphasise the 'end point', either utilising the formal system or healthcare-seeking behaviour. Secondly, some studies highlight the 'process,' which is how the system works (illness response or health-seeking

behaviour). Behaviours associated with seeking health care are examined with a special emphasis placed on obtaining "health care" by the official definition that applies in a given setting. Although data are also collected on self-care, visits to more traditional healers, and unofficial medical channels, these are frequently seen as something that should be avoided in large part, and the emphasis is placed on persuading people to choose official medical channels first (Ahmed et al., 2001). Tipping and Segall (1995) show that various socio-economic factors, including gender, age, the social status of women, the type of illness, access to services, and perceived quality of the service, influence the decision to engage with a particular medical channel. Other factors that play a role in this decision include the perceived quality of the service, access to services, and perceived availability of services.

In keeping with this history, various 'social cognition models' have been constructed to predict likely behaviour patterns. These are determined by a complex interplay of demographic, social, emotional, and cognitive variables, as well as perceived symptoms, accessibility to care, and personality (Conner & Norman, 1996). The fundamental presumption is that behaviour may be most effectively comprehended in terms of an individual's view of the social context in which they find themselves. People are said to engage in HSB when they conduct corrective activities to improve their health when they believe they are unhealthy. HSB is defined in this research as an action carried out by older persons who may have potential health problems to get or gain treatment

or assistance about their potential health problems from healthcare experts. As a corollary, HSB refers to deciding among the elderly while experiencing symptoms of illness, whether or not to seek professional medical attention from trained medical specialists.

Theoretical Framework: Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory (SET) is a psychological and sociological approach developed by social psychologists and sociologists to describe exchange as a process of negotiation between parties. The theory, which originated from Economics, Psychology, and Sociology, posits that human connections are formed by applying an individual's subjective cost-benefit analysis and evaluating available options (Homans, 1961). The works of two key theorists, George C. Homans and Peter M. Blau, inspired SET. According to these scholars, people are portrayed as strategic agents who use the resources at their disposal to maximise benefits/gains. They contend that people make decisions based on rational consideration by weighing the consequences of alternative courses of action in terms of the “profit” they are likely to generate. This, however, explains why people do the things they do.

The theory's central tenet is that social behaviour and interactions between people are the product of an underlying exchange process. This viewpoint indicates that pursuing rewards and benefits and avoiding costs and punishment forms the interaction between persons. This paper defines SET and then discusses how it might be

applied to the natural ageing process. According to Homans' thesis, which is founded on sociological and psychological viewpoints, social interaction may be seen as a kind of reinforcement. Individuals determine and learn from their previous interaction experiences whether their behaviours are rewarding or expensive. They do this by analysing the outcomes of those events. These behavioural consequences, whether favourable or unfavourable, reinforce, extinguish, or change future behaviours to accomplish desired results and reduce expensive effects. People have a tendency, as their relationships with others progress over time, to prioritise social interactions that result in favourable outcomes and to do their best to reduce the impact of those that have unfavourable effects. The principle of reciprocity in socially contractual commerce is the foundation for this approach. According to this criterion, every action or service that has some value to person B and is offered by person A to person B is anticipated to be returned by person B to person A, where the exchange expectation concerns some agreed-upon standard of equivalence (Gouldner, 1960).

According to this theory, individuals make choices by consciously or subconsciously weighing the benefits and drawbacks of a potential relationship or course of action, with the ultimate goal of optimising the amount of pleasure they get. This theory is not intended to measure behaviour or change on a societal level; instead, it focuses on face-to-face interactions between individuals. According to this theory, a person will weigh the cost of a social interaction

(a negative outcome) against the reward of that social interaction to determine whether or not to participate in the exchange (positive outcome). The costs and the benefits might take the form of something tangible, such as money, time or service. They can also be intangible, such as an individual's effort, the approval of their peers, love, pride, shame, respect, opportunity or power. Everyone expects they will get more from a conversation or connection than they provide. When a person feels that they are getting less out of a relationship than they put into it, they will choose to quit the relationship. However, they will maintain a connection if it is profitable enough for them to do so. It depends on whether something is sufficient or insufficient, such as the expectations of a person and their comparisons with other prospective interactions and partnerships. The idea that individuals anticipate fair treatment in exchange is an additional SET component. People expect to get the same return for bearing the same costs, and they feel dissatisfied when this expectation is not met.

The theory has been utilised in a wide variety of social contexts, including but not limited to romantic relationships, friendships, workplace behaviour, organisational management, business decisions, social power, leadership, politics, consumer purchasing decisions, and television viewing decisions, amongst others (Antonucci *et al.*, 2014; Cropanzano *et al.*, 2017; Gouldner, 1960). In this investigation, the theory will be used to explain the determinants of healthcare challenges among the elderly and the provision of healthcare services in Nigeria. Individuals learn from their previous interactions, evaluate their

current reciprocal or nonreciprocal exchanges, and make decisions about their future behaviours, all of which contribute to the development and accumulation of these perspectives on social exchange over time. This is one of the fundamental principles underlying these viewpoints.

Dowd (1975) developed an enhanced version of the fundamental SET to take into account the experiences of older adults. Accordingly, as people age, the ratio of rewards to costs associated with social interactions might shift based on social status (for example, being an elder) and personal resources. He argued that this could happen because people's social status changes as they get older (e.g., money, power, and the ability to work or provide care to others). Dowd emphasised the perceived loss of status and power that he claimed are linked with ageing in his exchange theory of ageing. This loss of status and power is related to ageing (Dowd 1975). He said that since one's resources (such as one's health, income, loss of employment and community responsibilities and others) diminish with age, elderly individuals are more prone to be involved in social transactions that are unequal or unbalanced. These unbalanced connections may lead to a power disadvantage for the older person, in which they are needed to depend or rely on others to satisfy their fundamental requirements. However, they are unable to give back (reciprocate) too much in exchange for the assistance they get.

According to this view, the HSB of older people is directly related to the quality of the relationships they maintain with their significant

others, governments and organizations that provide social services. It might be argued that as individuals age, their resources decrease, and it becomes more difficult for them to meet the demands of others around them in kind. The perception is that they are a burden rather than a benefit. These factors make it impossible to perform services on their behalf. As a result of globalisation, industrialisation, and technological advancement, there is a chance that relationships may deteriorate since individuals may believe they do not play a vital part in the world. The government may see investing in them as more of a cost than a benefit to the country. This connection risks their lives and prevents them from accessing necessary social and healthcare services. When such services are made accessible, they are asked to pay for them, which may discourage their HSBs. The nature of the Nigerian economic system is that it is capitalist, which means that individuals and governments alike are driven by the desire to accumulate wealth. Therefore, the HSB of the elderly may remain poor and negative when they are perceived by the elite or capitalists as burdens or not delivering any significant advantage or advancement. This may be the cause for the delayed development in the sponsoring, passing and implementing measures capable of standardising the health of the aged.

The family that also need to reciprocate the demands of their senior ones are motivated by the drive to generate more money. Hence, they leave their older ones in the care of housemaids or public institutions where abuse is easily perpetrated against this ageing population. Thus,

this leaves them with all types of psychological issues, comparing the mistreatment from the household they formed with their resources throughout their young age. Of course, when elderly persons keep being isolated and deprived of chances, social connection, and financial assistance, they begin to encounter psychological issues in the form of depression, and dementia, among other psychological obstacles. These issues may make it easier for natural challenges to one's physical health to emerge, such as falls, shingles, weight loss, loss of sight, hearing trouble, chronic illnesses, and infections, to name a few. The societal changes that have occurred throughout the years have positively and negatively affected the HSB of the ageing population. A robust economy has brought forth unprecedented levels of affluence for a large number of individuals in the current society of Nigeria. Because medical treatment has improved and is now more readily available, older people can survive longer. However, since older people cannot reciprocate the required resources, they are not as crucial to the economic survival of their families and communities as they formerly were. This is a change from the situation that existed in the past.

Even if the theory can explain the phenomena being investigated, this does not mean it is exempted from criticism. The theory has been criticised because it cannot provide an acceptable and appropriate explanation of the biological process of ageing. It is also assumed that every connection or contact is based on cost and advantages, which is another criticism levelled against it. This suggests that the culture

of caring for elderly persons allows it not only for economic reasons but also out of respect for old age and morality. Taking care of older people is seen as a moral and respectful act. The theory is criticised for heavily justifying the explanation of old age challenges within material gains by devaluing nonmaterial assets such as love and friendship. This is one of the major criticisms levelled against the theory. One more powerful argument against the theory is that it does not provide sufficient theoretical precision, which is of limited practical use.

Scholars who use SET can explain many social phenomena that have already occurred, but their ability to make valuable predictions regarding those phenomena is severely limited. Although the theory can explain many social phenomena that have already occurred, the theory is criticised for having overlapping constructs that need to be more clearly distinguished. The theory was found to have an insufficient appreciation of the positive or negative hedonic value of these various constructs; an assumption of bipolarity, which treats negative constructs (such as poor health and health challenges) as the absence of positive constructs (such as support and social services); and, following on from the previous three issues, theoretically inaccurate behavioural prediction (Cropanzano *et al.*, 2017).

The theory has been criticised, yet, this has not diminished its use in explaining the HSB of older people. The theory has theoretically explained its relevance to this research by assuming that the HSBs of the elderly are due to their incapacity to reciprocate the advantages or benefits acquired from members of society. It is

generally accepted that the difficulty of a situation increases proportionally to the recipient's inability to return the favours extended to them. In addition, the cost of maintaining relationships with older people is inversely proportional to the amount of engagement and assistance provided and the difficulty of such relationships. Nevertheless, the theory presupposes that older people can deal with the challenges by not solely relying on welfare services, government interventions, and support from significant others, rather, they must acknowledge their unavoidable condition and try to add value to other social issues. The theory proposes that an individual's life history and experiences, including age, gender, race, culture, and context, among other things, can prepare them for a new old age rather than viewing living longer as a circumstance that will inevitably result in a deficit.

Family is still essential to middle age and older people, and their stake in the family's future is also significant to them. However, people of middle and old age appear to be creating circumstances that will permit them to maintain reciprocal exchanges. These circumstances can be made by developing new short-term, contemporaneous relationships, such as service exchanges, or by developing multiple innovative long-term relationships, such as group or congregate housing. Either way, these people are putting themselves in a position where they can maintain reciprocal exchanges. Strong negative emotions such as anger and frustration are elicited among those who are concerned when this norm is violated because service, in return, is

denied or fails to meet an agreed-upon level of equivalence. This results in the sense of being mistreated unjustly. If the social relationship is threatened, or if it continues, strong negative emotions are elicited. The injustice of exchange in significant social role relationships can potentially have negative health impacts owing to the body's response to persistent stress when it occurs regularly. This provides more justification for the determinants of healthcare services and challenges among the elderly in Nigeria.

Methodology

Comprehensive, recently published scholarly works were reviewed by the authors to identify journal articles and books dealing with health, health-seeking behaviour, old age, ageing, and older adults to examine the health-seeking behaviour among the elderly. Also, research articles, case reports, report updates and other web pages were reviewed to examine the concepts of health-seeking behaviour. This approach was used to determine the health attitudes and perceptions of the elderly in Nigeria towards healthcare services. The database of WHO was accessed to determine the HSB of the aged population in Nigeria to arrive at a logical conclusion. Google advanced search was used to search the internet using several combinations of words and phrases such as gender, health, medical information and knowledge and Nigeria. The data extracted were thematically analysed and presented in narrative forms. The data were discussed in this review and recommendations were made based on identified gaps in efforts toward achieving optimal HSB and quality

healthcare among the elderly in Nigeria. This research did not involve human participants and the analyses were undertaken with publicly available secondary data; hence no ethics approval was required.

Discussion/Results

It has been discovered that factors that significantly affect HSB among the elderly include the types of health facilities, the distance to the nearest health facility, ignorance of disease due to old age, poverty, poor attitudes of health workers, lengthy treatment process, trust on god for healing if ill, living alone, and lack of someone to take them to hospitals (Adewoye *et al.*, 2021; Moe *et al.*, 2012; Ohta, 2021; Vagenas *et al.*, 2019). Physical, socio-economic, cultural, and even political factors can all play a role in influencing an individual's health behaviour (Vagenas *et al.*, 2019). Accordingly, the utilisation of a health care system may be contingent on the levels of education, economic factors, cultural beliefs and practices. Other factors include the environment, socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge about the facilities, gender issues, the political climate, and the healthcare system itself (Adewoye *et al.*, 2021; Ohta, 2021). Accordingly, environmental conditions, socio-demographic factors, and knowledge about the facilities.

According to Moe *et al.* (2012), HSB is impacted by a handful of characteristics, including illiteracy, misconceptions, money, family composition, social isolation, and reliance. These factors may amplify the level of misery and incapacity experienced by older

people. Adewoye *et al.* (2021), using a descriptive cross-sectional study to conduct research amongst 420 elderly respondents in Ido-Ekiti, with the assistance of an interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire, found that respondents' health-seeking behavioural practices were significantly associated with employment status, educational level, cost of health care, access to the health facility, length of time before consultation, beliefs, and lack of support from relations. The findings established that 63.3% of the respondents experienced an episode of illness within the most recent year before the study. However, only 35.3% of the respondents sought treatment from a physician (considered positive HSB). In comparison, 57.9% admitted to using self-medication, consulting a spiritualist, or using herbal medicine (poor health-seeking behaviour). The study concluded that most older people had poor HSB due to educational and economic factors. Specifically, the following subheadings are identified as vital correlates determining HSB among older people.

Society, Location and Environment

Because of advances in medical technology and general socio-economic circumstances, people are living longer than ever before. This has resulted in a more significant percentage of older people in the overall population of every nation globally. All of these things are dependent on the health-seeking behaviours of individuals, especially the behaviours of older people. Therefore, older persons need to engage in HSB to maintain maximum health. Increasingly

elderly societies need older individuals to manage many ailments by using various services (Ohta *et al.*, 2021). The HSBs of such societies will be different from one another depending on the healthcare resources that are readily accessible. People living in metropolitan regions, which have access to sufficient medical resources, have their pick of several different medical and healthcare providers. This circumstance may also be connected to the incorrect use of medical treatment.

Rural communities often do not have access to sufficient resources for medical treatment. When they encounter symptoms, they are required to assess the severity of those symptoms and select from among the significantly restricted medical resources and access to medical treatment. However, since there are not enough resources available, elderly persons may lack an understanding of medical care concerns (Goins *et al.*, 2015). In rural districts of a developing country, acute malaria, hypertensive crises syndrome, and acute hypertensive heart failure were the three conditions responsible for the greatest number of geriatric emergencies, according to the findings of a cross-sectional study (Vagenas *et al.*, 2019). A qualitative study by Ohta (2021) revealed that elderly individuals who lived in rural regions considered that being assisted in later life was a reward for having led a decent life. In addition, this group believed that official assistants could satisfy their requirements in a timelier and satisfactory manner if they were aware of and adhered to the guidelines for obtaining assistance among older people.

Education, Medical Information and Knowledge

Moe *et al.* (2012) used a cross-sectional survey to study the health status and HSB of 729 older people in Myanmar. They found that approximately half of the elderly population in Myanmar had primary or lower education; only one-third were working but with low income; and one-third of the male and female elderly perceived that they were in good health. The findings revealed that upper and lower Myanmar people had different behaviours when seeking medical attention. Accordingly, it was discovered that the elderly's behaviour towards obtaining medical attention was not connected with gender, race, or religion but rather with money and education level. There was a significant correlation between having a higher level of education and seeking professional treatment for depressive symptoms (Jett, 2012). Accordingly, a lower educational degree was connected with an increased risk of untreated morbidity caused by chronic illnesses. In terms of educational interventions, there was an increase in the use of professional treatment among those with mental problems who attended educational workshops (Jett, 2012).

People of advanced age may seek professional treatment for relatively minor symptoms without giving due thought to the extent to which they need medical attention. Consequently, people's knowledge and abilities about managing their minor symptoms may not be nurtured by the incorrect use of medical treatment, which may be the case. In addition, a lack of information and ability to deal with

symptoms might cause a delay in accessing medical treatment in instances of severe sickness. In addition, a lack of information resources and inadequate access to medical care expertise and locations might be barriers to HSBs, particularly among older individuals living in rural areas. Even though the internet and social media have made it simpler to get new information, a more significant proportion of people in their 20s and 30s than those in their 40s and 50s utilise these platforms (Molokhia and Majeed, 2017). Older people are more likely to get their news from television and newspapers, and fewer than half of them use the internet. If there is insufficient information, people might not seek professional care when they need it as much as they should, particularly for acute symptoms. The progression of symptoms may cause various diseases, leading to clinical issues such as multi-morbidity and polypharmacy (Molokhia and Majeed, 2017). As a result, insufficient information and healthcare services for older people living in rural areas may also affect their HSBs.

Finance, Income and Cost of Healthcare Services

People think of old age and poor health as two sides of the same coin. Due to the high cost, people avoid getting medical care from a doctor with a formal qualification. It is a significant factor in determining whether or not to seek treatment, the desired treatment, and whether healthcare providers are flexible in how they receive payment. Some of the factors associated with a delay in seeking medical attention include

the attributing of poor health to getting older, having a low economic status, and health workers having a negative attitude toward the care of elderly patients. Abdulraheem (2017) reported that over two-thirds of respondents sampled (68.8%) had never been to health facilities to receive medical check-ups. As a result, most of the people who participated in the survey cited the high cost of orthodox healthcare services, cultural beliefs, a lack of availability, and a significant distance between themselves and nearby health facilities as the reasons they did not use proper healthcare facilities.

Several studies (Adewoye *et al.*, 2021; Bhat and Kumar, 2017; Moe *et al.*, 2012) have shown a correlation between certain socio-demographic and socio-economic factors and HBS and practices. In a study that was carried out in Ilorin, Nigeria, Abdulraheem (2017) discovered that most older persons who were unwell resorted to self-medication. According to the findings of another study by Okojie and Lane (2020), which was carried out in a rural community in Nigeria and focused on the elderly population, most older people sought healthcare services from patent medicine stores, which is indicative of a lack of proactive or poor HSB. This is likely because of the high cost of seeking orthodox healthcare and unsatisfactory experiences with the quality of treatment received from conventional medical facilities. Their dissatisfaction was due to several factors, including the length of time it takes to get a consultation, the attitude of the staff members, the lack of availability of doctors, the uncleanliness of the hospital environment, the inefficiency of the hospital services, and the cost

of the hospital bills (Abdulraheem, 2017; Adewoye *et al.*, 2021; Okojie and Lane, 2020).

In a study conducted by Rummi *et al.* (2022) on the socio-demographic status, identification of the health-related determinants and health problems, and treatment-seeking behaviour among rural elderly, it was discovered that most respondents (93.91%) drank water from tube wells, 81.49% used sanitary latrines, and 42.68% were addicted to chewing betel leaf. The research adopted a cross-sectional descriptive method to collect data from 427 people aged 60 years at Baliyati, Mohishashi, and Dhalkunda villages in Saturia, Upazilla of Manikganj District. The majority of study participants suffered from chronic disorders such as joint pain (57.38%), vision disturbance (57.14%), general weakness (37.94%), sleeplessness (16.16%), and hypertension (14.50%), as determined by a technique of purposive sampling. Most respondents (78.68%) took action to address their health concerns; however, approximately 41.75% did not take any action when sick due to the prohibitively expensive cost of treatment. Most respondents who sought medical attention (55.6%) indicated a preference to check into a health facility run by the government. The findings revealed that the primary challenges faced by older people in Bangladesh were increased medical costs and a lack of knowledge regarding the availability of medical facilities in nearby medical centres. The study also found that most diseases could be avoided if awareness was raised through the use of mass media.

Age and Gender

In a different study that was carried out by Bhat and Kumar (2017), using a community-based cross-sectional study that was carried out in the field practice area of Father Muller Medical College, it was found that the majority of the participants (67.3%), who were in the age group of 60-70 years, were illiterate, and that approximately 65.3% of them were suffering from chronic illness, primarily hypertension. The research, which consisted of a purposive sample of 150 older people and data collection through a pretested questionnaire, concluded that most participants with chronic diseases went to a health facility consistently to keep track of their condition. The only demographic characteristic to be substantially connected with HSB for chronic disease in the research was the participant's age. This was determined using statistical tests such as chi-square and regression analysis.

There are several different ways in which gender influences HSBs. There was a correlation between being female and having a lower likelihood of seeking professional assistance for symptoms of depression (Jett, 2012). In addition, the possibility of female patients seeking treatment for different forms of mental illness was lower than that of male patients (Srivastava *et al.*, 2021). There was a correlation between having a lower educational level, a lower monthly income, and the existence of one or more significant medical issues and receiving less professional treatment for the symptoms of depression (Jett, 2012). When confronted with diverse diseases, people and communities behave

noticeably differently concerning their pursuit of medical care. For example, Adhikari and Rijal (2020) highlight contrasting pathways to care for women when faced with abnormal vaginal discharge, as opposed to malaria. For the former, the woman is bound far more by rituals and obligations, such as shaving before an examination and being accompanied to a medical consultation by her husband.

Personal Attitudes, Beliefs and Marital Status

The personal notion that one does not need medical care was the most common obstacle mentioned when it came to therapy for depression. Mistrust of mental health practitioners, the belief that treatment would not be beneficial, the fear of stigma, and an unwillingness to discuss intimate things with a stranger were all often cited as obstacles to receiving mental health care (Adhikari and Rijal, 2020). A favourable influence on HSBs was found to be familiarity with medical treatment and support from families. There was a correlation between knowledge of medicine and the practice of self-treatment (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Accordingly, the likelihood of having untreated morbidities was significantly lower in those who lived with a spouse than in those who lived alone. Ohta (2021) highlighted that conditions such as diabetes frequently require changes in lifestyle and approach to health behaviours. The ease with which such changes occur depends on the person's perception of their self-efficacy and expectations about their actions' outcomes. It is abundantly clear that this has a connection to HSB.

A paper on native and immigrant diabetes sufferers in Sweden reiterated the importance of self-efficacy in health-related behaviours and compliance and the cultural relativity of beliefs about health and illness (Ohta, 2021). Specifically, the paper focuses on the differences between native and immigrant diabetes sufferers. Despite this, Vagenas et al. (2019) claim that during consultations with diabetic patients, medical professionals typically fail to address the social or psychological issues associated with diabetes. Adewoye et al. (2021) bring up another interesting point in their study, which is that diabetic patients who have lower levels of trust in the medical professionals who treat them may be more likely to engage in hazardous behaviours to their health. This dynamic between the physician and the patient is thus brought up once more as an essential issue.

Type of Healthcare Facilities and Socioeconomic Correlates

According to a study on the HSBs of 411 older people carried out by Zabeen (2016), 45.7% sought treatment from a private hospital, 32.3% sought treatment from non-registered practitioners, and 18.9% sought treatment from a government hospital. The remaining 3.1% utilised home remedies or sought the assistance of traditional healers. The accessibility, low cost, and relative affordability of treatment were the primary influences behind their decisions. Educational intervention, gender, educational level, socio-economic status, past medical histories, personal belief, mistrust of mental health providers, stigma, health status, alcohol

consumption, utilisation of family practice, and living with families were significantly associated with HSBs among older people living in rural areas, according to several studies (Baral and Sapkota, 2018; Jett, 2012; Srivastava *et al.*, 2021).

Baral and Sapkota (2018) discovered that most participants (86.5%), using a cross-sectional analytical study to survey 104 elderly aged 60 years and above, accessed via a non-probability convenience sampling technique, were suffering from a chronic health problem. Of the participants, 37.8% suffered from hypertension, and 11.1% suffered from diabetic mellitus. The study, which gathered data by conducting interviews with older people at their homes and analysing them using descriptive and inferential statistics in SPSS software, found that all of the participants (100%) were seeking help for their health problems; however, 83.7% of the participants sought help from modern medication, and 16.3% sought help from alternative medicines. It was found that the health problem, ethnicity, and religion were each found to have a statistically significant relationship with the HSB. The research also reported that most participants were aware of requesting assistance from the health care centre. However, they still believed in alternative medicine rather than contemporary medication, which may be a disturbing reality in healthcare.

A low socio-economic position was another factor that hindered the effectiveness of HSB. It was noticed that having a poor socio-economic status was a barrier to receiving treatment for mental problems (Adhikari and Rijal, 2020).

Consequently, families with low incomes were related to a low treatment-seeking rate for chronic disorders. Because of their health issues, patients also used less self-care. Self-treatment for symptoms was connected with being in good health and not having consumed any alcohol recently (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). The likelihood of older persons with lower socio-economic levels seeking treatment for mental problems decreased compared to those with higher socio-economic status (Srivastava, 2021). There is a correlation between HSB and quality of life (QOL). People with a higher quality of life were less likely to use inpatient services (Brenes *et al.*, 2015). High quality of life was associated with familiarity with healthcare (Pham *et al.*, 2018). In addition, HSB, associated with a pattern of self-management for minor symptoms, was associated with a good quality of life (Ohta *et al.*, 2021).

Studies of HSB in connection to tuberculosis have frequently shown that older patients do not always pick a public health care institution, delay diagnosis, and often do not finish the extensive course of treatment required. According to research by Steen and Mazonde (1999), almost all patients in Botswana make their first appointment in a “modern” healthcare facility. Despite this, 47% of patients went on to seek treatment from a traditional or faith healer after beginning conventional treatment. They stress the significance of social and cultural factors as essential contributors to the outcome of tuberculosis control efforts. These patients have the misconception that tuberculosis is a “European disease” that can be effectively treated

with Western medicine. Despite this, a traditional healer is consulted to gain insight into the 'meaning' of the illness for the individual in question. In a similar vein, it was determined by Pronyk *et al.* (2001) that patients in South Africa suffering from tuberculosis were more likely to seek treatment at government facilities than they were for patients suffering from other conditions. 72% went to a hospital or clinic first for treatment, while only 15% went to a spiritual or traditional healer, and 13% went to a private doctor. Despite this, the authors acknowledged a significant failure by official clinical services to diagnose individuals who exhibited symptoms. This contributed even further to the already substantial issue of delayed presentation, which is especially prevalent among women.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Longer life gives chances and allows for further education, a new career, or a long-neglected passion for older people, their families, and communities. However, old age does not come only as an opportunity because it is laced with various health challenges that significantly impact the HSBs of older people. As individuals age, greater obstacles, life experiences, healthcare expenditures, financial security and changing circumstances increase health risks that require positive HSB and proactive strategies for prevention or minimisation. Age-related health crises affect older people's HSB, particularly their well-being, social interactions, decision-making, and self-control. A poor HSB encourages the postponement of treatment among the ageing population, leading to

community transmission risk. Thus, understanding HSBs assists the aged, public health practitioners, and policymakers in improving the healthcare system and health promotion programs.

This paper notes that multiple factors, including types of society, environment, education, medical information, knowledge, cost of healthcare services, age, gender, personal attitudes and marital status, have influenced the HSB of older persons. This paper concludes that adequate and proactive HSB can help older people adaptively change and live happy and productive lives. Adequate and consistent access to health facilities, socioeconomic position, and perceived service quality impact HSBs across demographic groups. Older people should seek more information about their health and exercise daily to stay energetic, independent, and happy. They should maintain a healthy lifestyle, accommodate for bodily function changes and prioritise preventative health behaviours by becoming immunised for health emergencies, obtaining frequent check-ups, and being optimistic about old age. Older people need to get abreast of arts, science, politics, and other cultural and social changes that may benefit their health. Also, they should be provided with free or subsidised health care and monthly financial aid to ease stress. More importantly, they should stay active, eat healthily, get enough sleep, limit alcohol, and manage healthcare.

References

- Abdulraheem, I. S. (2017). Health needs assessment and determinants of health seeking behaviour among elderly Nigerians. A household survey. *Annals of African Medicine*, 6(2), 58-63.
- Adewoye, K. R., Aremu, S. K., Ekpo, D. S., Akanbi, S. A. & Ibrahim, T. (2021). *Health seeking behavioural practices of the elderly in rural community of Ekiti State, South-western Nigeria*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1149361/v1>.
- Adhikari, D. & Rijal, D. (2020). Factors affecting health seeking behavior of senior citizen of Dharan. *Journal of Nobel Medical College*, 3(1).50-57.
- Agency Report. (2019, September 2). FG to establish six regional geriatric centres in tertiary hospitals. *The Punch*. <https://punchng.com/fg-to-establish-six-regional-geriatric-centres-in-tertiary-hospitals/>
- Ahmed, S. Adams, A. Chowdhury, M. & Bhuiya, A. (2000) Gender, socio-economic development and health-seeking behaviour in Bangladesh *Social Science and Medicine* 51(3), 361-371
- Akpan, I. D. & Umobong, M. (2013). An assessment of the prevalence of elder abuse and neglect in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Developing Countries Studies Online* 3(5), 10-15.
- Antonucci, T. C. Ajrouch, K. J. & Birdtt, K. S. (2014). The convoy model: Explaining social relations from a multidisciplinary

- perspective. *The Gerontologist*, 54(1), 82-92.
- Baral, R. & Sapkota, P. (2018). Health seeking behaviour among older people of Bharatpur Municipality of Chitwan District, Nepal. *Journal of College of Medical Sciences-Nepal*, 14(3), 150-153.
- Bausell, C. & Bausell, R. (1987). The internal structure of health-seeking behavior. *Evaluation Health Profession*, 10, 460-475.
- Bhat, S. & Kumar, S. (2017). Study on health care seeking behaviour among elderly in rural area. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, 6(2), 350-352.
- Bourne, P. A. (2009). Health status and medical care-seeking behaviour of the poorest 20% in Jamaica. *The International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine and Public Health*, 1, 167-185.
- Brenes, G. A. Danhauer, S. C. Lyles, M. F., Hogan, P. E. & Miller, M.E. (2015). Barriers to mental health treatment in rural older people. *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 23, 1172-1178.
- Chauhan, R. C. Kandan, M., Purty, A.J. Samuel, A. & Singh, Z. (2015). Determinants of health care seeking behaviour among rural population of a coastal area in South India. *International Journal of Scientific Reports*, 1(2), 118-122.
- Conner, M. & Norman, P. (1996). The Role of social cognition in health behaviours. In M Conner and P Norman (eds) *Predicting Health Behaviours: research and practice with social cognition models* Open University Press, Buckingham. 1-22.
- Cramer, R. J. Johnson, J. C. Crosby, J. W., Henderson, C. E., La Guardia, A. C., & Stroud, C. H. (2016). Personality, coping and mental health among lesbian, gay, and bisexual community members. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 96, 272-278. DOI: 10.1016/j.paid.2015.10.025
- Cropanzano, R. Anthony, E.L. Daniels, S.R. & Hall, A.V. (2017). Social Exchange Theory: A critical review with theoretical remedies. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11(1), 1-8. [Http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/annals.2015.0099](http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/annals.2015.0099)
- Doshi, A. M. Van Den Eeden, S. K. Morrill, M. Y., Schembri, M., Thom, D. H. & Brown, J. S. (2010). Reproductive risks for incontinence study at Kaiser Research Group. Women with diabetes: Understanding urinary incontinence and help seeking behaviour. *Journal of Urology*, 184, 1402-1407.
- Dowd, J. J. (1975). Aging as exchange: A preface to theory. *Journal of Gerontology*, 30(5), 584-594.
- Duner, A & Nordstrom, M. (2015). Intentions and strategies among older people: Coping in everyday life. *Journal of Aging Studies*, 437-451.
- Fonta, C.L. Nonvignon, L. Aikins, M., Nwosu, E. & Aryeete, G.E. (2017). Predictors of self-reported health among the elderly in Ghana: a cross sectional study. *BMC Geriatrics* 17, 171. DOI

10.1186/s12877-017-0560-y

- Goins, R. T. Williams, K. A, Carter, M. W. Spencer, M. & Solovieva, T. (2015). Perceived barriers to health care access among rural older people: A qualitative study. *Journal of Rural Health*, 21, 206–213.
- Gouldner, A. W. (1960). The norm of reciprocity: A preliminary statement. *American Sociological Review*, 25(2), 161–78.
- Hampshire, K.R. Porter, G. Owusu, S.A. Tanle, A. Abane, A. (2011). Out of the reach of children? Young people's health-seeking practices and agency in Africa's newly-emerging therapeutic landscapes. *Social Science & Medicine*, 73(5), 702–10.
- Homans, G. (1961). *Social behavior: Its elementary forms*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Ibitoye, O.G. Sanuade, O.A. Adebowale, A.S., & Ayeni, O. (2015). Psychological well-being of the elderly in Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 12(1), 74-85.
- Jett, K. (2012). Making the Connection: Seeking and receiving help by elderly African Americans. *Qualitative Health Research*, 12, 373–387.
- Kahana, E & Kahana, B. (2011), Successful aging among people with HIV/AIDS. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 53-56.
- Lloyd-Sherlock, P. (2022). Aging and health policy: global perspectives In: Lee K, Buse K & Fustukian S., Eds. Health policy in a globalising world. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 195-207.
- Moe, S. Tha, K., Naing, D. K. S. Htike, M. M. T. (2012). Health seeking behaviour of elderly in Myanmar. *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, 4(8), 1538-1544.
- Mojoyinola, J. K. & Ayangunna, J. A. (2012). *Social work and welfare in aged in Nigeria*. Adults and Aged in Nigeria, 19-29.
- Molokhia, M. & Majeed, A. (2017). Current and future perspectives on the management of polypharmacy. *BMC Family Practice*, 18, 70.
- Mudiare, P. E. (2013). Abuse of the aged in Nigeria: Elders also cry. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(9), 79 -87.
- Obinna, C. (2021). UBTH inspires good health for aged with geriatric services. *The Vanguard News*.
<https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/03/ubth-inspires-good-health-for-aged-with-geriatric-services/>
- Ohta, R. Ryu, Y., Kitayuguchi, J. Sano, C., Könings, K. D. (2021). Educational intervention to improve citizen's healthcare participation perception in rural Japanese communities: A Pilot Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18, 1782.
- Okojie, P. W. & Lane, R. (2020). Health care options and factors influencing health seeking behaviour in a rural community in Nigeria: A cross-sectional study.

- Christian journal for global health*, 7(2), 83-84.
- Okumagba, O.P. (2011). Family support for the elderly in Delta State of Nigeria. *Studies on Home and Community Science*, 5(1), 21-27.
- Olayiwola, I.O, Oganah, B.C, Ojo, T.G. & Akande, T.O. (2013). Knowledge of population ageing and elderly nutrition among undergraduates in a Nigerian university. *International journal of Education and Research*, 1(8),1-12.
- Ouwehand, C. Ridder, D.T. D. & Bensing, J.M. (2017). *A review of successful aging models: Proposing proactive coping as an important additional strategy*. Utrecht University, Utrecht, The Nether-lands, 873-884.
- Pham, T. L. Nguyen, T. X. Nguyen, H. T. T., Nguyen, T. N., Nguyen, T. H. T., Nguyen, Q. N., Tran, B. X., et al. (2018). Sex differences in quality of life and health services utilisation among older people in rural Vietnam. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16,69.
- Poortaghi, S. Raiesifar, A. Bozorgzad, P. Golzari, S. E. J., &Parvizy, S. (2015). Evolutionary concept analysis of health seeking behaviour in nursing: A systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research*, 15, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-015-1181-9>.
- Pronyk, P. M. Makhubele, M. B. Hargreaves, J. R. Tollman, S. M. & Hausler, H. P. (2001) Assessing health seeking behaviour among tuberculosis patients in rural South Africa. *International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, 5, 619-627.
- Rickwood, D. & Thomas, K. (2012). Conceptual measurement framework for help-seeking for mental health problems. *Psychology Research and Behaviour Management*, 5, 173–183.
- Rummi, F. H. Khan, M. M. Tahsin T, et al. (2022). Pattern of geriatric health problems and health care seeking behavior among rural people in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Family & Community Medicine*, 6(2), 74?79. DOI: 10.15406/ijfcm.2022.06.00268
- Shaw, C. Brittain, K. Tansey, R. & Williams, K. (2018). How people decide to seek health care: A qualitative study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 45, 1516–1524.
- Srivastava, S. Sulaiman, K. M. Drishti, D. & Muhammad, T. (2021) Factors associated with psychiatric disorders and Treatment Seeking Behaviour among Older people in India. *Sci. Rep*, 11, 24085.
- Steen, T. W. & Mazonde, G. N. (1999). Ngaka yasetswana, ngakayasekgoa or both? Health Seeking Behaviour in Batswana with Pulmonary Tuberculosis. *Social Science & Medicine*, 48, 163-172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(98\)00329-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(98)00329-3)
- Straud, C. McNaughton-Cassill, M. & Fuhrman,

- R. (2015). The role of the five-factor model of personality with proactive coping and preventative coping among college students. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 83, 60-64. doi: 10.1016/j.paid.2015.03.055
- Tipping, G. (2000). *Healthcare seeking behavior in Asian transitional economies: A literature review and annotated bibliography*. Development bibliography 17. Institute of Development Studies, England.
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2019). *World Population Prospects 2019*.
- Vagenas, D. McLaughlin, D. & Dobson, A. (2019). Regional variation in the survival and health of older Australian women: A prospective cohort study. *Aust. N. Z. J. Public Health*, 33, 119–125.
- World Health Organization. (2021 October). *Ageing and health*. WHO Fact Sheets. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health#:~:text=Common%20conditions%20in%20older%20age,conditions%20at%20the%20same%20time>.
- Yeung, N. Y. Lu, Q. Wong, C. Y. & Huynh, H. C. (2016). The roles of needs satisfaction, cognitive appraisals, and coping strategies in promoting posttraumatic growth: A stress and coping perspective. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 8(3), 284-292. doi:10.1037/tra0000091
- Zabeen, S. (2016). Health Care Seeking Behaviour in Southwest Ethiopia. *Journal of Rural Health and Health Seeking Behavior*, 32(3), 28–30.
- Zhang, T., Liu C. & Ni, Z. (2019). Association of access to healthcare with self-assessed health and quality of life among old adults with chronic disease in China: Urban versus rural populations. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 16, 2592.